

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

50
YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Cedefop study on individual learning accounts

The main findings

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Cedefop's study on individual learning accounts (ILAs)

Objective

- Explore the potential for developing ILAs in selected EU Member States and provide support to stakeholders in designing and implementing ILAs

Key activities

- Develop analytical framework
- Conduct five in-depth case studies - Austria, Estonia, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands - including country-specific scenarios and policy reflections
- Formulate general policy guidelines

Defining individual learning account

Adult learning systems*: The orchestra metaphor**

*Desjardins & Kalenda (2025)

**suggested by Bernd Käßlinger

Countries with substantial schemes supporting individual adult learning

- Broad target groups
- High level of support:
 - annual grant exceeding PPP 500 EUR or
 - high one-off grant (higher than 70% of mean income)

- At least one substantial instrument for individuals
- No substantial instrument
- Not covered

Source: Based on [Cedefop Financing adult learning database](#)

Countries selected for the case studies

Identifying the space for ILAs: based on the existing financing arrangements

- Emerging, ex-post considerations based on individual country reflections
 - Need to further consider country- and/or region-specific variability
1. Presence of substantial public financing schemes (embedded in the methodology of the study)
 2. Only/primarily supply-side only or both supply- and demand-side schemes (the basis for clustering)
 3. Gaps in coverage of such schemes (specific considerations based on eligibility)

Finding the place for ILAs: based on the types of training provision to be supported

1. Formal education of 6 months+ (often part of initial education)
 - *High cost; long-term training leave or part-time work arrangements; subsistence costs*
2. Extended intensive non-formal E&T up to 6 months (often provided by PES)
 - *Average cost, long-term training leave, subsistence costs*
3. **Extended non-intensive non-formal E&T**, e.g. language courses, modular courses
 - *Average to low cost, critical to assure continuity over multiple years*
4. **Short-duration courses to develop work-relevant skills**, e.g. IT, soft skills, driving
 - *Low cost; large variety; need to ensure relevance and quality; possible overlap with category 5*
5. Job-specific training (mostly employer-provided/sponsored)

Countries with established demand-side instruments

	Space available for ILA	Potential way forward
the Netherlands	Public (co-)financing instrument for the whole working-age population to support participation mainly in short courses (type 3 and 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reform STAP • Integrate the budget of STAP into regional LM structures/ vouchers schemes • Introduce ILA at national level
Germany	Public (co-)financing instrument for the whole working-age population to support participation mainly in short courses (type 3 and 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reform and expand the Upgrading Training Assistance • Implement the proposed federal instruments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - demand-side scheme (direct costs of CVET) - long training leave (subsistence costs) • Introduce 'CVET insurance'
Austria	Public (co-)financing instrument for the whole working-age population to support participation mainly in short courses (type 3 and 4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand supply-side funded framework for AL • Introduce national ILAs for CVET combined with regional (demand-side) financing instruments • Introduce 'employment insurance'

Countries without extended demand-side instruments

	Space available for ILA	Potential way forward
Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less favourable conditions for a new demand-side financing instruments • Significant space for scaling-up existing mainly supply-side instruments and strengthening the 'enabling framework' 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a single online portal • Scale-up the provision of micro-credentials • Establish paid training leave
Estonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less favourable conditions for a new demand-side financing instruments (available for some target groups) • Significant space for scaling-up existing supply-side instruments and strengthening other areas of AL relevant for ILAs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand existing financing instruments • Strengthen the link between LM needs and public funding for AL • Establish quality assurance system for all AL providers

* But with existing substantial supply-side schemes

Zooming in – Public Funding Arrangements supporting Individuals *(not including wage replacement/subsistence costs)*

(tentative symbols only; tax incentives not reflected)

Netherlands

STAP
EUR 190 Mio
(2022)

No estimate on the total public spending available

Germany

*AufstiegsBAföG

Upgrading Training*
EUR 295 Mio
(2019)
911 Mio
(2024)

Estimate (2015) – about 6 billion

Austria

Regional ILAs
EUR 35 Mio
(estimate 2023)

Estimate 600 Million (excluding subsistence costs)

Cross-country conclusion – Group with ILA-type experiences

- Demand-side funding always plays a specific yet supportive role, with more funding delivered via other types of instruments
- Instruments present in the countries do not meet the indicated levels of support of the ILA Recommendation (and the supporting impact assessment study) in some ways – but also exceed them in others
- Experiences with demand-side instruments allow for some insight into what one can expect by the approach in a particular environment
- While there is considerable advocacy to extend public funding for adult learning, the implementation of a novel ILAs would most likely be only one desirable extension among others
- An ILA approach requiring disproportionately high levels of public funding might imply a risk of causing an imbalance between existing funding arrangements

Zooming in – Public funding arrangements supporting individuals (not including wage replacement/subsistence costs)

(tentative symbols only; tax incentives not reflected)

Ireland

No estimate on total spending available
– Spending of the (levy-based) National Training Fund – about EUR 700 Mio (2020)

Estonia

No estimate on the total spending available

Cross-country conclusions

- By defining activity types and paying providers per ‘study place’, systems can ensure both the availability and diversity of learning options while preserving individual choice—thus blending supply- and demand-side elements
- Demand-side co-funding widens learner choice but requires clear eligibility rules and quality assurance, which can be harder to enforce in less-regulated segments

Many countries address this by offering catalogues of free or low-cost learning opportunities, often forming a core pillar of adult learning support

ILAs – support for individually selected, job-related AL

The employer as the point of reference

- Work as the biggest facilitator of job-related adult learning
- Employer-sponsored training/CVET (38,8%)

Publicly funded, formal (job-related) adult learning

Lower estimate
5-13 %/year

Individually selected, job-related adult learning (with co-funding by individuals)

Job-related adult learning provided by the PES/as part of ALMP

Other points of reference

- Learning for current tasks/challenges
- General adult learning

Back to the reference case: The reformed Individual Learning Account (*Compte Personnel de Formation*) in France

GRAPHIQUE 1 | Entrées en formation CPF par année, entre 2020 et 2024

Note: données 2020, 2021, 2022 et 2023 révisées depuis la dernière publication « Le Compte personnel de formation en 2023 », Dares.

Lecture: les entrées en formation CPF augmentent de 4% entre 2023 et 2024, pour atteindre 1 387 500.

Champ: France; entrées en formation CPF.

Source: SI-CPF, extraction mars 2025, traitement Dares.

- All (formerly) employed persons (15+)
- EUR 500 / EUR 800 per year
- Accumulation possible for up to 10 years
- An EUR 100 minimum individual contribution introduced (from May 2024)
- Database of eligible courses: 184 500 offers (2024) from 13 700 providers (average fee EUR 2 300 for 89 hours)
- Budget applied: 2022 – EUR 3.0 billion / 2024 – EUR 2.1 billion

[Le compte personnel de formation en 2024 - une année marquée par plusieurs réformes](https://politiques-sociales.caissedesdepots.fr/sites/default/files/Breves_34_V4_Pages.pdf)

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‘Interlude’

- Current funding arrangements across the analysed EU MS are highly complex
- Introducing a new ILA would mark an important step towards realising the right to individual access to adult learning – nevertheless, there are related, yet, differently designed options as well
- It would require the mobilisation of substantial additional public resources for adult learning
- For any novel ILAs, the right place within the “instrument section” would be required – keeping the overall “balance”
- The effectiveness of a new ILA will also rely on the performance and availability of the other components of the overall “orchestra”, as captured by the ‘enabling framework’
- Given the size of the required reforms, a step-by-step approach spanning a longer period may be the best way forward

Designing and implementing ILAs – step by step

1. Conduct preparatory work

- Stock-taking of adult learning system
- Forecasting funding

2. Identify the space for intervention ILA within the existing system

- Are there similar schemes already existing
- To what extent the existing schemes cover both short and long courses?
- Are there any gaps in the coverage (e.g. specific target groups)
- Are the existing mostly demand-side or supply-side?
- How would a new ILA scheme interact with the existing schemes?

Designing and implementing ILAs – step by step

3. Design the instrument

- Fully-fledged, full-scale ILA in line with the Council Recommendation
 - Range of the group entitled
 - **Size of annual entitlement**
 - **Potential mandatory (minimal) individual contribution**
 - Preferential treatment for specific target groups
 - **Accumulation of the entitlement**
 - Range of eligible learning opportunities
 - Costs for administrative controls and decision making
- Smaller, complementary ILA-type instruments
 - e.g. limited budget instead of an entitlement, no accumulation but higher levels of support for particular learning opportunities, specific groups, etc
 - initial piloting designs as the basis for working towards fully-fledged ILA
- Expanding the current financing instruments

Designing and implementing ILAs – step by step

4. Strengthen training leave and support for subsistence costs
 - short-term training leave where employees continue receiving their wages; public contributions to employer's wage costs
 - unpaid long-term educational leave and receiving income replacement/ contribution to living costs
5. Reinforce other elements of the enabling framework
6. Close other key gaps in adult learning system
7. Negotiate a policy package; develop multi-year implementation plan
8. Create governance structures
9. Set up continuous monitoring
10. Review with stakeholders

Thank you

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